
Cash Flow Forecasting Mechanisms in Joint Stock Companies in International Practice

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Abstract: this article will discuss the methods of forecasting cash flows in joint-stock companies of our country, the essence of financial cash flows, the history of the development and origin of methods of forecasting cash flows in joint-stock companies of our republic, as well as the analysis of its advantages and improvement of development prospects. The article also presents the existing problems in the methods of forecasting cash flows, as well as the author's recommendation approaches and suggestions for their elimination.

Key words: finance, management, joint stock companies, company, foreign markets, financial control, cash flows, fixed capital.

Introduction.

The world's largest companies the ability to determine payment of financial strategy planning, valuation samaradoligini net cash flows, liquidity, free cash flow using the method in determining the status of conducts scientific research in the field. The main capital of the company, working capital and depreciation change in forecasting cash flows and given that the costs of free cash flow discounted cash flow method, using the current value of the future cash flow of the company, the assessment of the income tax before paying interest and to determine the company's net operating profit after tax was paid reinvestisiyani directed to calculate and to determinethe company's cash flows in making forecasts of the impact of internal and external factors evaluation of the main focuses of scientific studies in this area is.

The joint-stock companies in uzbekistan forecasts of cash flows, the method of making large enterprises state owned shares in improving on the stock exchange being the main focus of the privatization process by placing the primary and secondary mass. In particular, "the state share of existing enterprises and international financial institutions to attract foreign investors in the privatization process to" [1] were set the task of. Consistent and effective implementation of this task is to attract foreign investors in the country, the state-owned large enterprises to significantly increase the weight, money akisiyadorlik of resources in society to ensure transparency, cash flow samadorligini determine the use of modern methods of discounted cash flow and free cash flow makes possible a comprehensive.

Thematic analysis literature

The joint-stock companies cash flow the concept of scientific-theoretical approaches, joint stock company specific aspects of the self, free cash flow, adiscounted cash flow ktsiyadorlik society of scientific-theoretical importance of covering scientific and methodological aspects are given.

Foreign scientists economists Brigxemning eyes, joint-stock company known during the time of the cash flow the net cash flow is that when we look at transforming. With regard to this, it was noted that the flow of capital to evaluate the cash flow formed [2]. Additionally, scientists, economists, which is one form of obamacare, joint-stock company cash flow is returned to the investor in the form of cash, representing the effects of their investment, which is the main

indicator of society. The joint-stock companies on investment cash flow net of the spread of the network of the benefits, tangible and intangible assets depreciation amount was formed from [3]. In turn, breaks and they gave the following definition in their research identified vice cash flow: "the joint-stock companies and economic activities cash flow from reduced production of proceeds from sales of the product to come out of the product costs, other costs and taxes, is determined by the multiplication of [4]" in our opinion, joint-stock company the cash flow of the investment project implementation and the performance of the assets of money funds, which is a society formed as a result of receipts and distributed on time payments. Also, the joint-stock companies are mainly three cash flows from activity has been formed. In particular, cash flow from financial activities, cash flow from investing activities and cash flow from the main business is composed of.

Xaker foreign scientists economists and others I have used in the definition of free cash flow research and two joint-stock companies are mainly discussed the deficiencies of the valuation of free cash flows. According to their opinion, "free cash flow - which is more than the cost of capital net operating cash flow this second definition, the equivalent of one a man had two sons, but net operating cash flow discretionary cash flow is added to the..."pointed out. Also, Philip according to research, the joint society of the society of operating fixed assets net working capital and free cash flow from the cash flows is equal to the growth of ayirma pointed out. In his eyes, in determining net working capital and free cash flow by considering fixed assets should get the change of society. The reason asossiy main influencing factors in the calculation of free cash flow working capital means.

Research metodologiyasi.

Abstraktsiyalash scientific research, gruhlash, comparison, including covers and perspective, empirical analysis and to use other methods led. In the article the way for the use of the financial instrument using the method of scientific abstraktsiyalash islam is the legal basis for the improvement of organizational theoretical, scientific and practical importance was induced. Also, the comparison in the comparative method in practice in the advanced countries of the world and the society in the joint of ways to make cash flow forecasts for the use of the method of organizational-the legal basis of appropriate conclusions based on comparing with available in our country has formed.

Analysis and results

The joint-stock companies and to identify the direct analysis method of cash flow cash flows chiqimi kirimi, as well as current obligations and investment allows us to assess mablag'mavjudligini mablag'mavdujlighi enough to pay additional. Investisya foliyati harakterlash with negative cash flow was the reason long-term assets of the society and to attract the joint major in investiyalarni ko'rasatadi that the expansion of production. In particular, joint-stock company net cash flows to the cash flows by the direct method for the assessment of the society samaradoligini should be considered. The joint-stock companies are mainly considering the taking of cash flows as shown in the cash flow report is carried out. In particular, joint-stock companies operating activities, investing activities and financial activities cash flows, funds from taking on reports shall be formed. Additionally, joint-stock company in the country in the forecast of the cash flow net cash flow of the movement of the price change and the effects of influencing factors are analyzed. In addition, the joint planning and effective management of the financial resources of society should be to forecast cash flows.

1-table Comparison of direct and indirect cash flow method [5]

Cash flow direct method	Indirect method cash flow
report cash flow method for the formation of only cash operations, cash flows Directly, in particular, uses of funds and the proceeds of the money spent	is usually used as the basis indirect method, net income, assets and liabilities are added or changes in the yard, and then non-cash expenses are added to
net income in the cash and non-cash money will take the equivalent of	automatically converted to cash flow, net income and
cash flows Direct method has features that take into account all the factors. In particular, non-cash depreciation costs into account to what extent the effects of money and cannot operations	and uses operating activities cash flow indirect method gepotezalardan takes into account all of the factors in the calculation of
immediate cash flow report because the report is very clear on the correct work which is not included and therefore, the cash flows that will require less time for the preparation of the report	on cash flows indirect method may not be considered because this report takes into account the correct method to prepare the cash flow of workers and usually takes more time
and less popular among accountants report on the immediate cash flow is less used by organizations and businesses	become more and more popular among accountants report on the indirect cash flow, is used by more organizations and businesses

Free cash flow net investment joint stock company is mainly in determining costs, capital costs, working capital and depreciation costs of taking out the change are enhanced calculate the free cash flow will determine the possibility of society's. Also, and most importantly a decrease of influencing factors in the growth of free cash flow net investment costs, capital costs, made changes in working capital and depreciation cost. In particular, joint-stock company free cash flow is an indicator of the activities of the society. All cash receipts of income of joint stock company in the form of free cash flow, net of all costs in the form of common funds and allows you to identify reinvestisiya done all funds for business development.

Income and balance sheet information of the business to receive long-term growth forecast will help. Comparison of indirect and direct cash flow method are listed in the table 1 above. The report on the method of preparation of cash flows cash flow direct and indirect method. Joint-stock companies are able to choose any method to report. In particular, the report on the existing situation completely and business standards, regulatory requirements that must be answered from the standpoint of compliance requirements associated with it. The popularity of indirect cash flow method usually provides to the accuracy of cash flow forecasts and, therefore, cash flow compared to immediate popular. There are direct and indirect methods of cash flow analysis. Direct cash flow method in the analysis of joint funds through the funds of the society from the review of business information, add money to the positive and negative is formed. In this method the joint-stock companies of the capital that is associated with the entrance and the output shows the flow of money. Also, the economic activity of the society was guruhlash cash. As a result, net cash flows for the reporting period which indicates information form.

In general, the direct method of cash flow and cash flow analysis to identify chiqimi kirimi, as well as enough to pay current obligations and investment allows us to assess the possibility of additional mablag'mavdujligi mablag'mavjudlik. You don't have to be net cash flow positive for the activities of the society. However, investment activity is characterized by negative cash flow, the reason long-term assets of the society and be involved in major investment in the expansion of the network that the joint production ko'rasatadi. Current cash flow should be positive but the stock and the financial community. In turn, the activities of the society from positive, as well as the society suggest that the further development of its activities. In particular, joint-stock company

valuation of net cash flows by the direct method, it is necessary to consider the effectiveness of the flow of money to the society.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In our opinion, the joint-stock company, mainly in determining the free cash flow net of investment costs, capital costs, made the change and calculate the depreciation costs of taking out are enhanced working capital, free cash flow will determine the possibility of the society.

Joint stock Company from the effective use of working capital free cash flow shows how. The return of the reduction of the increase in working capital free cash flow, therefore the effective use of working capital to purchase the assets of the society joint suggest that low income. Joint stock company the same amount of free cash and working capital also increase the amount of assets and cash flows are growing and growing information ko'rstadi therefore the fact that on a permanent basis. Therefore, the growth of working capital and free cash flow of the flow of money will remain to service the society paralel continuously growing.

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